

An Adaptive NeRF Framework for City-Scale Emergency Awareness

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Abstract. Rapid situational awareness during disasters such as floods, earthquakes, and wildfires demands 3D scene representations that can update seamlessly as new aerial data arrive. Neural Radiance Fields (NeRFs) are a technique that constructs such 3D scene representations. Conventional NeRF-based pipelines remain static and require full re-training when additional observations become available, leading to delays that hinder real-time decision-making. In this paper, we introduce a city-scale NeRF framework for high-speed adaptation and real-time rendering under rapidly evolving data conditions. Our approach combines three key components: meta-continual learning (MCL) for fast adaptation without catastrophic forgetting, modularized neural architectures to support large-scale spatial decomposition, and optimization based on Instant Neural Graphics Primitives (Instant-NGP) for efficient training and compact representation. Together, these components enable real-time refinement of city-scale NeRFs as new observations become available.

Keywords: NeRFs, Continual Learning, Meta-Learning

1 Introduction

Effective disaster response relies on rapid, accurate, and continuously updated situational awareness. During emergencies such as floods, earthquakes, or wildfires, aerial drones serve as critical assets for collecting visual information over large and often inaccessible areas. However, traditional 3D reconstruction and visualization pipelines remain fundamentally static: they require full retraining whenever new data arrive, depend on large curated datasets, and cannot adapt in real time to continuously streamed, heterogeneous observations. These limitations introduce significant delays in updating 3D scene representations, impeding first responders’ ability to assess structural damage, locate survivors, and coordinate timely operations.

Neural Radiance Fields (NeRFs) offer high-fidelity, photorealistic 3D scene representations, yet standard NeRF training is ill-suited for emergency conditions. Updating a NeRF with new data typically requires either retraining from scratch or performing costly fine-tuning that may overwrite previously learned knowledge. Moreover, city-scale environments exceed the memory and training capacity of a single network, necessitating strategies for spatial scalability.

To address these challenges, we propose a city-scale NeRF framework designed for continuous, real-time adaptation under extreme data conditions. Our system integrates three foundational components that jointly enable scalable, stable, and high-speed updating of large 3D environments:

- **Meta-Continual Learning (MCL).** Building on Meta-Continual Learning of Neural Fields (MCL-NF) [18], our approach combines meta-learning with continual learning for long-term knowledge retention. Meta-learned initialization encodes geometric and radiometric priors, while sample-aware weighting prevents catastrophic forgetting during updates. This allows the model to incorporate new observations while maintaining global photometric consistency.
- **Spatial Decomposition for City-Scale Representation.** Inspired by Mega-NeRF [15], we decompose the environment into spatially localized NeRF modules. Each module is optimized independently, and only those intersecting observations are updated at runtime. This modularization reduces computation, prevents interference across regions, and supports efficient large-area mapping.
- **Instant-NGP for Rapid Optimization.** Each module uses an Instant-NGP [8] backbone, whose multiresolution hash encoding and lightweight multilayer perceptron (MLP) allow fast convergence and compact representation. This design enables the incorporation of streamed drone imagery in near real-time, with each expert being represented by an extremely compact network.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section 2 reviews prior related work. Section 3 overviews our proposed two-phase framework. We describe the offline and online stages of our approach in Sections 4 and 5, respectively. Section 6 presents the method’s experimental evaluation, while Section 7 describes the viewer integration to render the trained NeRFs. Section 8 offers concluding remarks and discusses potential future directions.

2 Related Work

A key obstacle in continual learning is catastrophic forgetting. Prior work identifies three major families of mitigation strategies for this phenomenon [17]. Regularization-based methods, such as EWC [6] and Fisher-weighted formulations [18], constrain parameter drift through importance weighting. Parameter-isolation approaches include CL-NeRF [19], which introduces a lightweight expert adaptor and conflict-aware distillation, and SCARF [16] which offers task isolation through scene-specific latent matrices generated by a shared hypernetwork. Finally, replay-based methods such as Instant Continual Learning [10] perform generative replay by using a frozen NeRF as a generator of pseudo-labels for past views, enabling self-distillation without storing raw data.

Another field of research that has shown great promise is meta-learning. Gradient-based meta-learning algorithms—namely MAML [1, 3] and its first-order variants [9]—aim to learn a generic parameter initialization that enables rapid adaptation. Recent analyses [12], along with La-MAML [4] and ANML [2], highlight a growing recognition that the mechanisms enabling fast adaptation

Fig. 1. Overview of the proposed city-scale NeRF infrastructure.

are aligned with those required for continual stability. Building on this connection, MCL-NF [18] unifies meta- and continual learning by learning a shared initialization for sequential tasks and using regularization to mitigate forgetting, allowing neural-field experts to adapt quickly without losing prior knowledge.

The idea of deploying specialized expert modules has been driven by the need to scale neural fields to large and heterogeneous environments. Modularization enables per-region updates and rendering performance that decouples from scene size. Block-NeRF [13] achieves this by dividing urban scenes into independently trained spatial blocks, Mega-NeRF [15] forms distributed experts through data-driven spatial clustering, and Switch-NeRF [7] introduces a learnable gating network that routes 3D points to a mixture-of-experts (MoE) [5] for adaptive decomposition. Instant-NGP [8] provides a highly efficient hash-grid encoding and lightweight MLP backbone, enabling expert modules to train orders of magnitude faster while remaining compact at scale.

3 Method

Our work is related to Meta-Continual Learning of Neural Fields (MCL-NF) [18], which introduces a generic framework that combines modularization, meta-continual learning, and FIM-loss regularization to mitigate catastrophic forgetting. While we draw inspiration from their design principles, our objective differs: we focus on time-critical data scenarios where reconstructions must update rapidly as new observations arrive. Thus, rather than adhering to the strict sequential-task protocol of MCL-NF, we decouple processing into two phases (Fig. 1).

In the *Offline Phase*, we proactively exploit a static dataset under normal conditions by partitioning it into spatial shards and meta-training region-specific initializations on the entire dataset at once. This pre-deployment process removes the requirement to learn tasks sequentially without revisiting them, providing a comprehensive, high-quality reconstruction prior. In the *Online Phase*, local

Fig. 2. Example of meta-learned NeRF initialization for a single spatial region. The real scene (left) and the corresponding meta-learned representation (right). The model learns a coarse, structured prior rather than a detailed reconstruction.

initializations are rapidly adapted to newly arriving observations, enabling immediate updates while being resistant to catastrophic forgetting. To further accelerate adaptation, we integrate Instant-NGP primitives, allowing the use of more efficient, compact models than those employed in MCL-NF.

The complementary components of *modularization*, *meta-learning*, and compact *Instant-NGP* models are unified in this work in a dual-phase pipeline for *adaptive city-scale 3D reconstruction*. The offline and online phases are presented in detail in Sections 4 and 5 and summarized in Algorithm 1.

4 Offline Stage: Meta-Learning

The offline stage (Lines 1–21 of Alg. 1) produces an initialization that captures the coarse geometry and appearance of the environment. A drone-captured dataset is partitioned into spatial regions, each assigned to an expert NeRF. Each expert is trained on its isolated partition to form regional priors encoding the dominant scene structure (see Fig. 2). The resulting priors allow the online stage to focus solely on refining local details rather than relearning the entire scene.

4.1 Data Preprocessing

Since our data consist of real-world drone imagery, a necessary step is to recover camera intrinsics and poses under a consistent world coordinate frame. We use COLMAP [11] to estimate Structure-from-Motion (SfM) geometry, producing geo-aligned camera parameters and a unified reference frame for all images. For each image, rays are generated and paired with ground truth RGB values.

In our modularized setup, rays are assigned to the region of an expert following Mega-NeRF’s routing principle, where each ray is routed to all regions that it intersects. To reduce boundary artifacts, regions are expanded by a small margin (for example, by 5–15%), allowing rays near borders to be shared across neighboring experts. This strategy produces a dedicated regional dataset for each expert, discarding rays that fall outside its region and yields compact, spatially coherent training subsets with lower memory and compute requirements.

Algorithm 1 Meta-continual pipeline with modularization.

Require: $p(\mathcal{T})$ Distribution over tasks
Require: Spatial regions $\mathcal{C} = \{1, \dots, C\}$ and, for each $c \in \mathcal{C}$: tasks \mathcal{T}_c , parameters θ_c , and expert neural field $f_c(\mathbf{x}) \equiv f(\mathbf{x}; \theta_c)$.
Require: Hyperparameters: batch sizes $|S|$ and $|Q|$, learning rates η_{inner} and η_{outer} , inner loop iterations K

Offline Stage: Meta-Learning

- 1: **while** not done **do** ▷ each iteration processes all regions
- 2: **for each** region $c \in \mathcal{C}$ **do**
- 3: Sample task batch $\mathcal{B}_c \sim p(\mathcal{T}_c)$
- 4: **for each** task $T_i \in \mathcal{B}_c$ **do**
- 5: Sample support S_i and query Q_i sets
- 6: Initialize Fisher Information Matrix F_i for task T_i
- 7: **Inner loop (Task-specific Adaptation)**
- 8: **for** $k = 1 \dots K$ **do**
- 9: Compute predictions: $\hat{\mathbf{y}} = f_c^{(k-1)}(\mathbf{x}), \quad \forall (\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) \in S_i$
- 10: Compute FIM weight w_{fim} .
- 11: Compute FIM-weighted loss: $\mathcal{L}_{\text{inner}}^{c,i} \leftarrow \frac{1}{|S|} \sum_{(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) \in S_i} (w_{\text{fim}} \cdot \|\hat{\mathbf{y}} - \mathbf{y}\|^2)$
- 12: Update fast parameters: $\theta_c^{(k)} \leftarrow \theta_c^{(k-1)} - \eta_{\text{inner}} \nabla_{\theta_c^{(k-1)}} \mathcal{L}_{\text{inner}}^{c,i}$
- 13: Update Fisher Information Matrix F_i .
- 14: **end for**
- 15: **Query Evaluation**
- 16: Compute task i loss: $\mathcal{L}_{\text{meta}}^{c,i} \leftarrow \frac{1}{|Q|} \sum_{(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) \in Q_i} (w_{\text{fim}} \cdot \|\hat{\mathbf{y}} - \mathbf{y}\|^2)$ as in steps 9–11
- 17: **end for**
- 18: **end for**
- 19: **Meta-update**
- 20: Update expert initialization: $\theta'_c \leftarrow \theta_c - \eta_{\text{outer}} \nabla_{\theta_c} \left(\frac{1}{|\mathcal{B}_c|} \sum_{T_i \in \mathcal{B}_c} \mathcal{L}_{\text{meta}}^{c,i} \right) \quad \forall c \in \mathcal{C}$
- 21: **end while**

Online Stage: Runtime Adaptation

- 22: **for each** incoming view batch I **do**
- 23: Ray generation: $R \leftarrow \text{GenerateRays}(I)$
- 24: **for** $k = 1 \dots K$ **do** ▷ as in steps 9–13, ray-based
- 25: Sample support rays $S \subseteq R$
- 26: Compute routing weights $G_c(S) \quad \forall c \in \mathcal{C}$
- 27: Compute expert predictions $\hat{\mathbf{y}}_c \leftarrow f_c(S) \quad \forall c \in \mathcal{C}$
- 28: Blend output $\hat{\mathbf{y}} \leftarrow \sum_{c=1}^C G_c(S) \cdot \hat{\mathbf{y}}_c$
- 29: Compute loss; $L \leftarrow \frac{1}{|S|} \sum_{(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) \in S} \|\hat{\mathbf{y}}(\mathbf{x}) - \mathbf{y}\|^2$
- 30: Update experts: $\theta'_c \leftarrow \theta_c - \eta_{\text{inner}} \nabla_{\theta_c} L \quad \forall c \in \{c \in \mathcal{C} \mid G_c(S) > 0\}$
- 31: **end for**
- 32: **end for**

Meta-learning is inherently task-driven, thus rays are further grouped into localized adaptation problems. To define tasks, we partition the experts’ regions into fine-grained 3D cells. Rays are assigned to the cell having the largest portion of their trajectory. During training, two disjoint subsets are sampled from a cell’s ray pool comprising a task. The first is called support and is used to teach the network to reconstruct a task from given views, while the second is called query and is used to evaluate generalization to held-out views from the same task.

4.2 Meta-Learning Objective

Each spatial region c is assigned to an expert with initialization parameters θ_c . From the regional task distribution $p(\mathcal{T}_c)$, we sample (Line 5 of Alg. 1) tasks $T_i = (S_i, Q_i)$ consisting of a small support set for task adaptation and a disjoint query set for evaluation. For every task, adaptation always begins (Line 6) from

the same initialization, i.e., $\theta_c^{(0)} = \theta_c$. The expert then performs K inner-loop updates (Lines 8–14) on the support set minimizing the Fisher-weighted loss [18]:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{inner}}^{c,i} = \frac{1}{|S_i|} \sum_{(x,y) \in S_i} w_{\text{fim}} \|f_c(x) - y\|^2,$$

yielding temporary parameters $\theta_c^{(k)}$, termed fast weights.

During inner-loop adaptation, only the MLP weights are updated, while the hash encodings remain frozen. This is motivated by two factors: (i) the multi-resolution hash grids act as stable, spatial feature priors shared across tasks, and should not overfit task-specific variations, and (ii) freezing them drastically reduces the number of trainable parameters, making each adaptation step faster.

The weights of the final inner-loop iteration $\theta_c^{(K)}$ help compute the meta-loss on the query set (Line 16), and only the initialization parameters θ_c are optimized in the outer loop. To scale this step to large outdoor scenes, we employ the First-Order MAML (FO-MAML) approximation, treating $\theta_c^{(K)}$ as a constant during the meta-gradient computation (Line 20) which avoids second-order derivatives, thus significantly reducing memory and computation overhead.

4.3 Continual Learning Properties

While our approach is oriented primarily towards meta-learning, it applies two mechanisms to tackle forgetting. First, spatial modularization isolates updates to the experts whose regions receive new observations, preventing cross-region interference. Second, Fisher-weighted gradients suppress changes to parameters that are important for stable scene structure, mitigating forgetting within a region. This combination ensures both inter- and intra region stability.

5 Online Stage: Runtime Adaptation

The online stage of Runtime Adaptation (Lines 22–32 of Alg. 1) specializes the meta-learned model. Unlike the offline stage, this phase does not construct tasks, partition datasets, or optimize a meta-objective. Instead, the system operates as a unified NeRF model, in which all experts function as components of a single shared NeRF, queried jointly over the full spatial domain. This eliminates the need for dual meta-optimization during deployment and focuses computation solely on rapid updates—essentially performing only *inner loop* adaptation.

At deployment time, novel drone imagery arrives in batches. Incoming views are preprocessed using COLMAP to estimate intrinsics and poses. Rather than rebuilding a new scene, we incrementally update the representation derived from the offline images while preserving the global coordinate frame, avoiding the substantial computational and latency cost of starting from scratch.

Ray generation produces the adaptation ray set R (Line 23), on which the model adapts for K iterations. In each iteration, a support set $S \subset R$ is sampled (Line 25). As in Section 4, rays in S are forwarded to all experts whose

spatial region they intersect (Line 26), with the boundary margin m controlling cross-region sharing. This produces routing weights $G_c(S)$ for each expert. Hard routing ($m = 1$) assigns each ray to exactly one expert, while soft routing ($m > 1$) blends multiple experts using inverse-distance weighting.

Each activated expert computes its prediction $\hat{y}_c = f_c(S)$ for the rays it receives (Line 27). These predictions are then blended into the container NeRF output (Line 28) according to the routing weights:

$$\hat{y}(S) = \sum_{c=1}^C G_c(S) \hat{y}_c, \quad \sum_c G_c(S) = 1.$$

This blended output is compared to the ground truth RGB values to compute the reconstruction loss (Line 29):

$$L = \frac{1}{|S|} \sum_{(x,y) \in S} \|\hat{y}(x) - y\|^2.$$

Only experts with non-zero routing weight receive parameter updates (Line 30):

$$\theta'_c = \theta_c - \eta_{\text{inner}} \nabla_{\theta_c} L, \quad \forall c \in \{c \in \mathcal{C} \mid G_c(S) > 0\}$$

6 Experiments

We evaluate our framework during runtime adaptation and measure the quality and speed of adaptation to novel views. We also benchmark our method, termed *Ours*, against a contemporary baseline, denoted as *NeRFacto-Incre*, which is NeRFacto [14] under the same time-constrained, incremental-view protocol. Both *Ours* and *NeRFacto-Incre* are initially trained on the same set of 249 images, and then evaluated on their adaptability to new images.

Models & Optimization. All experiments use Instant-NGP experts composed of two two-layer MLPs (one for density and one for color), each with 64 latent channels, paired with a multiresolution hash-encoding of 20 levels and a maximum spatial resolution of 4096. Meta-training is performed for $20k$ iterations using $K = 8$ inner-loop updates per task. We optimize with Adam, using learning rates of 0.001 for the MLPs and 0.01 for the hash-encoding during meta-training, and 0.005 and 0.02 during runtime adaptation.

Dataset. We use a drone-captured dataset. The captured region spans approximately $400\text{m} \times 450\text{m}$, corresponding to a city-scale urban area with mixed building structures, vegetation, and roads. For meta-learning, we collect 250 images of which 80% are used for meta-training and 20% for meta-validation. For runtime adaptation, we use a separate set of 55 images captured during *a different season*, enabling assessment under natural appearance changes. All images are downsampled to a resolution of 512×384 due to memory constraints.

Hardware. All experiments are run using a NVIDIA A10 GPU (23 GB VRAM), an Intel Xeon Silver 4310 CPU (48 cores, 96 threads), and 256 GB of RAM.

Code Availability. The implementation and all materials of the proposed framework are available at <https://github.com/psklavos1/adaptive-city-nerf>.

Fig. 3. Qualitative adaptation progress. Adaptation on 55 novel views at steps: {0, 100, 200, 400} with times measured from the start of optimization.

6.1 Adaptation Efficiency

We now evaluate runtime adaptation behavior of our framework under time-sensitive conditions. The focus is oriented towards the speed and accuracy of our approach to adapt on an updated environment with just a few novel views. To emulate a realistic update scenario, we take data from a different season with updated objects and colors.

Qualitative Behavior. As shown in Fig. 3, regions with noticeable changes are highlighted at each step to make the progression easier to follow. The first 100 steps of the optimization constitute the slowest phase, also incurring the cost of ray-generation. Seasonal appearance begins adjusting almost immediately (100 steps), with certain geometries fading out (e.g., the cars near the top) and new structures gradually emerging (e.g., the blurry truck in the bottom-right region). Adaptation accelerates over the next 100 steps, during which major geometries become clearly established, albeit still exhibiting color and sharpness inaccuracies. At 400 steps (requiring *less than 1 second per image*), the scene stabilizes and the colors of newly introduced elements are refined.

Quantitative Behavior. We now provide our framework with five novel views of an updated scene captured from different positions to evaluate the speed and accuracy of adaptation on new information. As shown in Table 1, the first steps (up to 16) exhibit nearly identical runtimes due to their limited computational load, after which the runtime increases almost linearly with the number of optimization steps. The reconstruction quality reaches a satisfactory level at about 512 adaptation steps, with PSNR indicating a substantial reduction in reconstruction error relative to the ground truth, and corresponding improvements

Table 1. Test-time optimization (TTO) performance. Quantitative results on adaptation to a novel scene at different TTO steps.

Metric	TTO Steps												
	1	2	4	8	16	32	64	128	256	512	1024	2048	4096
PSNR (dB)↑	16.29	17.23	18.17	18.30	19.56	21.05	22.41	23.96	25.86	27.46	28.82	30.20	31.73
SSIM↑	0.51	0.53	0.53	0.53	0.57	0.63	0.66	0.69	0.73	0.77	0.81	0.84	0.87
LPIPS↓	0.53	0.52	0.52	0.53	0.57	0.52	0.50	0.46	0.40	0.34	0.28	0.22	0.16
Time (s)	1.19	1.30	1.60	1.85	1.99	2.61	4.08	7.17	13.33	28.38	54.91	107.23	212.41

Fig. 4. Quality of reconstruction. Side-by-side outputs of NeRFacto-Incre and our method at the same adaptation time.

observed in SSIM and LPIPS. This aligns with the qualitative results in Fig. 3, where users can already identify the key scene changes after 400 steps. Subsequent steps refine quality further if additional processing time is available.

6.2 Comparison with NeRFacto-Incre

We now present a comparison with NeRFacto-Incre under the same incremental benchmark. After both methods are trained to convergence on the initial area of interest, we evaluate their adaptability when 55 images from the central building area, captured in a different season, become available. The comparison focuses on: (a) reconstruction quality under identical adaptation time, and (b) the ability to preserve regions that do not appear in the incoming views, reflecting real-world conditions where each data batch may cover only part of the scene.

Fig. 4 shows that both methods are able to reconstruct the area receiving new observations, with no missing structures. However, our approach is able to reconstruct the scene more cleanly, producing sharper geometry and avoiding artifacts and blurriness. While NeRFacto-Incre exhibits better color fading, consistent with the seasonal shift, this difference is localized only to color saturation without affecting scene comprehension, and can be attributed to the meta-initialization retaining some color bias.

Crucially, Fig. 5 shows that our method preserves the reconstruction of regions that receive no new observations. The incoming images are concentrated around the central building area. NeRFacto-Incre successfully reconstructs this updated region, but gradually degrades structures elsewhere. In contrast, our method maintains the appearance of unobserved areas while also propagating

Fig. 5. Catastrophic forgetting evaluation. Methods are queried to showcase areas that receive no new observations after adapting to novel views.

the seasonal change across the wider scene due to the updated illumination. This provides an additional benefit: by the time images from other scenes arrive, the global seasonal adaptation has already been incorporated.

It is important to note that this experiment does not show the full forgetting-mitigation potential of our method. Spatial modularization restricts updates to experts whose region receives new observations, by design preventing unintended forgetting in irrelevant experts. However, in this experiment incoming data deliberately depict scenes where all experts overlap, inducing gradient updates to all of them. Consequently, our pipeline demonstrates robustness even under the challenging scenario of joint expert updates, preserving undistorted representations in parts of the scene that are not observed.

7 Rendering

To visualize our learned neural fields, we integrate a lightweight interactive renderer built on *nerfview* and the *viser* backend, exposing a real-time 3D viewer with dynamic camera control. Instead of querying a single NeRF, our renderer queries the container model, which internally performs spatial routing and blends expert outputs to produce the final color prediction. All volumetric rendering operations—ray sampling, accumulation, and color integration—remain unchanged. This enables real-time view synthesis across the entire covered area.

Operation Modalities. The viewer exposes two modes: (i) **View-Model**, enabling free navigation and inspection of the area, and (ii) **Runtime-Adaptation**, which enables streaming updates and visualization during online learning (Sect. 5). Users can toggle between exploring a static model or observing a live one.

Interactive Controls. A graphical control panel enables real-time adjustment of rendering and learning parameters as shown in Fig. 6. Rendering options include resolution and frame rate targets, output buffers (RGB, depth, and density accumulation), and near-far range clipping to constrain ray sampling bounds. Navigation controls support instant re-centering, horizon alignment, top-down view, and pose resets for rapid scene traversal. Additionally, users can isolate

Fig. 6. Viewer instance demonstrating the interactive control API. On the left, we have the rendered view, and on the right, the interactive controls.

individual spatial experts by visualizing the output of a single submodule, or switch to the blended multi-expert rendering to validate integration behavior. During runtime adaptation, additional controls unlock learning configuration, such as step count, learning rates, batch sizes, checkpoint export, and GPU utilization controls like active rays and discrete samples per ray.

8 Conclusions and Future Extensions

In this work, we introduced a two-stage framework designed for rapid adaptation across large-scale environments. Our framework incorporates spatial modularization for scalability and localized adaptation, meta-learning for establishing a strong initialization that enables fast refinement, and Instant-NGP primitives for high efficiency. Our experiments demonstrate rapid adaptation in both quantitative metrics and visual reconstruction across a broad range of test-time optimization (TTO) budgets, and when compared to optimized NeRF implementations our method outperforms them in the time-constrained setting both in adaptation quality and forgetting mitigation.

The combination of compact MLP structure and scalable modular architecture provides a foundation for future extensions to bandwidth-constrained, federated NeRF settings, where multiple drone agents could collaboratively update a shared scene representation in real time without direct data exchange.

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